

MANAGEMENT OF FINANCIAL RISKS AFFECTING THE COMBING OF ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article aims to highlight the theoretical foundations, categories of risks affecting the activities of enterprises and the analysis of the factors that make them possible. In this case, the algorithm for monitoring risks and the stages of analysis of enterprises using their financial statements are widely analyzed.*

It is based on the fact that joint-stock companies and limited liability companies are obliged to regularly monitor the amount of net assets. If the amount of net assets is less than the authorized capital, it has been analyzed that society is obliged to reduce its authorized capital to the level of net assets.

Keywords: *enterprise, risk, financial reporting, algorithm, equity, net capital, probability, risk, enterprise risk management (ERM).*

This means that the degree of influence of risks in achieving high results by increasing the efficiency of production in enterprises will certainly occur. Therefore, as enterprises increase the source of income, the level of risks affecting them also increases.

In many studies carried out, special attention is paid to the processes of assessing the degree of impact of risks affecting the activities of enterprises. In particular, "the interdependence of risk factors demonstrates its priority: changes in a given factor also affect changes in other factors, and consequently also change their impact on risk levels. In the process of risk management, the mechanism of risk assessment in small business enterprises is of particular importance, and the risk that affects the results of entrepreneurial activity is calculated. Risk assessment is the quantitative and qualitative calculation of the level of risk. First of all, entrepreneurial risks should be assessed quantitatively and qualitatively". Economist scientist T. In Malikov's work, "based on these important concepts of risk, we can say that the problem of managing business risks of enterprises is constant, especially in conditions of instability in the country, so it is an important tool to achieve economic goals and achieve the desired result."

"Currently, the effectiveness of an enterprise is largely determined by its management, that is, the ability of individuals to carry out activities aimed at protecting the enterprise from crisis processes and situations that lead to a decrease in profit. Due to objectively existing uncertainty, enterprises are forced to work at risk. To ensure the economic security of the enterprise, first of all, it is necessary to proceed from the risks that determine it." The results obtained show that in the studies done, "Risk Management affecting the economic security of enterprises has regional and sectoral characteristics. Measures aimed at minimizing risks will be much more effective in one region than in another. Therefore, in each specific case, first of all, it is necessary to take into account external factors - the regional and network affiliation of enterprises, and only then internal factors - the individual characteristics of the company. The presented methodology can be applied both for rapid testing of the size of risks under the relevant indicators and for the risk management process", with a focus on the risk management process. Risk management is very different from Strategy Management. Risk management focuses not on opportunities and successes, but on

negative sides - threats and failures. This contradicts the culture of "fulfillment", which most leading communities try to develop in the implementation of the strategy. And many leaders tend to discount the future; they do not want to spend time and money now so as not to face an ambiguous problem in the future. In addition, risk reduction usually involves resource allocation and investment diversification, which is contrary to the intensive direction of a successful strategy. For these reasons, most companies require a separate department for Strategic and external risk management. The size of the risk management department varies from company to company, but the team must report directly to the top team. As risk management tools, the following have been proposed:

- excessive-impenetrable risk management;
- insurance-the possibility of compensation for material damage caused by the occurrence of risk;
- hedging is the transfer of price risks from one company to another;
- distribution-the distribution of risk between the parties to the transaction;
- diversification-reduction of total risk by allocation of investments and/or liabilities;
- minimization-maintaining the balance of assets and liabilities in order to minimize fluctuations in the net value of the portfolio.

John Mainard Keynes was one of the first to classify risks. Keynes argues that all risks intersect closely with each other. Currently, one of the options for classifying risks is mandatory in specialized literature, which is devoted to the issues of economic, financial and organizational stability of the enterprise. In most cases, the selected criteria are not sufficient to cover all types of risks, but a number of fundamental types of risks are found in textbooks and scientific articles. Based on this information, it is customary to classify a subset of risks based on general concepts.

Thus, most of the authors identify the following risks:

- operation risk (possibility of economic losses under conditions when the enterprise does not use borrowed funds);
- market risk (risk of loss of the enterprise due to inconvenience changes in the market value of working capital, as well as the rates of foreign exchange rates (precious metals, securities, etc.), loans and deposits;
- financial risk (the possibility of negative financial consequences in the form of loss of income or capital in the event of uncertainty in the conditions for the implementation of financial activities).

Financial risks can be divided into:

- currency risk;
- credit risk;
- investment risk.

To these main risks are added several more options that arise in one order or another:

- business risk (uncertainty in the size of investments, cash flows in production activities and the value of the liquidation of assets, regardless of how the investment is financed);
- liquidity risk (difference between the Real price of the transaction and the market price);
- legal risk (losses as a result of changes in legislation, tax system, etc.);
- risk associated with regulatory authorities.

When determining the source of risk, it is necessary to determine the potential presence of this threat to the enterprise. The source of danger can be internal and external. When determining

the degree of impact of a risk, it is understood what can and to what extent it can affect a particular object. At the stage of determining the affected area, it is necessary to build scenarios for the further development of events, as well as assess the consequences of a particular event for other enterprise objects. At the same time, both the possibility of transferring the impact of risk to other objects and the onset of the consequences associated with this risk are considered. The construction of these scenarios requires a lot of resources and takes into account the interaction of a huge number of factors:

Enterprise risks are risks that arise as a result of unfavorable changes in the economy of an enterprise. Common risks:

changes in market conditions,
unbalanced liquidity (inability to meet payment obligations on time),
changes in management levels, etc.

The activities of the enterprise are influenced by risks in the form of phenomena (action) that prevent the achievement of commercial goals (strategic, tactical). Risks include factors that differ in the time or place of occurrence, the way of manifestation and the degree of influence on the work of the organization. As a result of their effect, there may be an unfavorable situation with the following manifestations:

lost (lost) profit;
direct loss;
lack of activity results;
an event in which you can lose or lose income in the future.

Another important indicator in the activities of enterprises is their net assets. Net assets are the assessment of the property of an organization that is generated from its own sources of funds. Net assets reflect real capital, their absolute value and positive dynamics characterize the stability of the financial situation of the organization.

"Net assets are determined by removing its total liabilities from the total assets of the enterprise. The amount of net assets fully corresponds to the authorized capital of the enterprise. In a non-profit organization, net assets are divided into unrestricted net assets and limited net assets".

The positive dynamics of the value of net assets is an important assessment indicator of the growth of the attractiveness of the company investiture, a market indicator of its financial stability, which in turn can increase the quotes and activity of transactions with its securities in the financial market. In western practice, net assets or net worth known as net worth is a net asset indicator that is the main indicator of the activity of any commercial organization. The net assets of the organization must be at least positive. Negative net assets are a sign that the organization is insolvent, indicating that the company is completely dependent on creditors and does not have its own funds.

Net assets should not only be positive, but also exceed the authorized capital of the organization. This means that during its existence, the organization did not waste the funds originally invested by the owner, but also ensured their growth. Net assets less than authorized capital are allowed only in the first year of activity of newly established enterprises. In the following years, when net assets are less than the authorized capital, the Civil Code and the legislation on joint-stock companies require that the authorized capital be reduced to the amount

of net assets. If the authorized capital of the organization is already at a minimum, the question of its further existence is raised.

"Net assets can be increased by increasing the charter, reserve or additional capital, or by reducing the founder's debts to the enterprise."

Joint-Stock Companies and limited liability companies are required to regularly monitor the amount of net assets. If the amount of net assets is less than the Authorized Capital, society is obliged to reduce its authorized capital to the level of net assets.

As we noted above, the probability of the occurrence of risks affecting the activities of enterprises can be through each indicator. Another important indicator in the activities of enterprises is its own capital, the change of which also leads to the development of risky situations. The movement of the enterprise's own capital is also characterized by relative indicators-the coefficients of revenue and output, which are determined as follows:

Rate of Return = amount of increase (increase) of equity / balance of equity at the end of the year

Output coefficient = the amount of a decrease (decrease) in equity / the balance of equity at the beginning of the year.

Having the indicators entering each of the stages of the analysis of similar enterprises using their financial statements in a positive state helps to avoid the risks that may arise.

The main issue in research on the issues of assessing the impact of risks on the activities of enterprises through internal and external factors is that it will be necessary first to draw up a classification of internal factors, and secondly to draw up a classification of external factors. First of all, focusing on the theoretical basis of influencing risks with various factors, this risk is the embodiment of anything that creates obstacles on the way to achieving certain goals. Depending on the type of risk present in a particular situation, it can be due to internal factors or external factors. Risk management is one of the main tasks that must be completed once it is identified and known. Risk and income are directly related to each other, that is, increasing one then increases the other and vice versa. Effective risk management leads to a more balanced trade between risk and reward for a better position in the future.

In research on the factors that influence risks on the activities of the enterprise, some scientists believe that this is primarily due to the need to improve the business management system. In Particular, S. Ermasov and others noted that " risk management throughout the enterprise has become popular due to the awareness of the leaders and owners of the enterprise that the business continues to grow risks. The peculiarity of Enterprise Risk Management is that it is aimed not only at solving narrow local problems within the framework of individual structural units or business cycles of the company, but also its goal is, ultimately, to create a corporate system of control of both "quantities". In addition, the risk management system should be considered not as a separate task, but as part of changes in the overall corporate management system, the purpose of which is ultimately to increase business efficiency."

Thomas Barton and other economists believe that it is necessary to divide risk exposure levels into two groups. In their opinion, " it will be worthwhile to divide the risks affecting the activities of enterprises into two groups. In this case, endogenous risks affecting the enterprise are associated with the external environment. The latter argue that exogenous risks are those that directly affect the internal functioning of the enterprise."

In other studies, it is necessary to associate risks affecting the activities of enterprises with activities in the market, in which they say that "the most important category of risks affecting Enterprises is associated with their activities in the securities market, which, if their influence is high, will lead to a sharp change in the price of shares of the enterprise".

Economist scientist D. Pickford believes that "the highest occurrence of risks affecting businesses will be linked to their income. The higher the income the enterprise achieves, the higher the level of risks affecting it. The risks of this category dramatically affect the liquidity, profitability and their net income of the enterprise."

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